

Growth of Homestay and Its Impact on Economy: A Study on Darjeeling District

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Abstract

Today, homestays have become a critical part of tourism in many countries and even an important local tourist attraction. Popularly known as the homestays, such home sharing arrangements between the resident-host has not only accorded newer dimensions to the sharing economy but it also heralded a new facet of the socio-cultural engagements among the visitors. The homestays are also positioned to provide tourists with a sense of feeling at home, interaction with the host family, first-hand relationship with locals, the experience of the local culture and low-cost accommodation. Homestays are becoming increasingly popular owing to their potential to provide either direct/alternative income to local communities, support local empowerment, tackle poverty, and attract eco-tourists by showcasing local culture and natural heritage. The homestay programme has evolved as an instrument for employment generation and economic development of a local community. Economic empowerment is important because it enables the host residents to be rewarded with a significant proportion of the financial benefits from tourism. Local communities generate income directly and indirectly through homestay programmes, which also empowers them by providing local employment, poverty alleviation, attracting tourists and enriching the experience of tourists by showcasing the natural and cultural heritage of the destination. It provides employment opportunities for the local populace and uplifts their standard of living. Through this research paper, the growth of homestays would be highlighted especially in the North Bengal region explaining such conditions.

Keywords Homestay Programme, Eco-tourist, Hospitality.

Introduction

Darjeeling is a town in India's West Bengal state, in the Himalayan foothills. Darjeeling is one of the best hill stations in Bharat which beckons a huge chunk of domestic and foreign tourists every year. The name 'Darjeeling' came from the Tibetan words, 'dorje' meaning thunderbolt (originally the sceptre of Indra) and 'ling' a place or land, hence 'the land of the thunderbolt'. Darjeeling is famous throughout the world for the tea it grows and the great view of the Kanchenjunga range of mountains that it offers. It is also known for its richness in cultural & natural heritage and the famous [toy train](#) that has been declared a UNESCO heritage.

On 15th June 2016, the Government of West Bengal announced to promote Home-stay through organic farming in Darjeeling hill town . It is a place or area of the house where the owner offers the tourists to stay as long as they want in exchange for money. This is a unique experience which is completely different from general hotel accommodation and stay. Homestay offers both food and lodging making the tourists part of the owner's family which is not experienced in hotels. This business has become very famous among the tourists and at the same time a source of income for the unemployed people of Darjeeling Hills. Homestay is now-a-days the most booming business in this area.. With huge success the government of West Bengal again revised the West Bengal Homestay Tourism policy in 2019 (26.12.2019) making it more convenient by involving more people so that employment generation can be created among unemployed people more. The added value attraction is the freshly made food to order, the warm smile of the owner that gives tourists a feeling of Home away from Home. This popularity, rather the craze of staying in these kinds of Homestays has created a massive positive impact on the economy of the place. Other than this, the aspect of comfort in terms of woollen garments here is also famous, such products are well knit and sold by the local people especially the women. The colours, designs, and the wool itself are so uncommon in their attractiveness, that tourists buy them readily. These small scale industries generate quite an amount of revenue that help the children of the local people of the state/ township to get education at a higher level.

Homestay concept is particularly found in rural areas that include both the exciting cultural and the natural sites of the region. These kinds of initiatives invite tourists to experience and witness the culture of the offbeat sites and also to inject money directly into the economy of these areas. The owners of the homestays generate additional income by providing the resources which are already with them, that is their own home area, to the tourists. Homestays are also considered as small-scale enterprises and the hosts as micro-hospitality entrepreneurs. The supplementary income generated for hosts in rural areas contributes to economic and community development in the entire region. The importance of the homestay concept has received attention from public and private stakeholders and interest groups because of the clear opportunities it represents in the economic development of the area. It helps in raising the standards of living of the local population both directly and indirectly. The tourism industry has experienced fast growth and rapid changes in recent times. It has become one of the leading industries of the world and is still growing at an increasing pace.

It is very important to note that the homestay concept is not new to India. It is from the ancient times that the doors of the family were always open to the visitors. This was an era when no one had even heard about the concept of commercial accommodation and the guest was considered equivalent to God.

Reasons behind the success of Home-Stay

An Informal Place

A home stay is simply a part of someone's home converted into a stay. It is less intimidating than a large impersonal hotel. It gives a feel of comfort and as if one is in their own relatives' home.

Personalised Attention

Case studies show that a visitor can attain his/her needs easily in such stays. One does not receive such a hospitable gesture in any hotel.

Experience A Place

No one knows a place better than a local. He can expose one to local sights, streets and foods which probably one won't get in a travel guide. Online research is good but it generally never beats local information.

Get The Best Home-Cooked Food

India has rich cuisine. Every few miles the food gives a new aroma and flavour. Staying local gives one a chance to try something new. Most of the time, here one has access to the kitchen and can learn their secret recipes from the host. While outside, getting home cooked food is such a wonderful experience.

Make New Friends

Staying in a Home Stay gives one a chance to meet people from different cultures and habits. It becomes more enjoyable as it is like a social gathering with only a few people to interact. It makes vacation a lot of fun and gives good friends probably forever.

Learning New Things

When one chooses to stay in home stays, one gets a better chance to mix with the local people and know more about their cultures and traditions.

It's Peaceful

Home stays are typically located away from the noise and clutter of cities. They rarely have more than 4 rooms. So even if it is full, one doesn't see many people around. Just being there is peaceful as these unfrequented, less populated areas offer a restoring solitude.

Gives A Sense Of Safety

Since one is staying with a family, safety becomes a big concern for the host because his personal reputation is at stake which is very important for them.

Responsible Tourism

By staying at a homestay, one contributes to the livelihood of the local community. In places like Darjeeling, Sikkim and Ladakh one mostly depends upon local stays and it's a way of some extra income for them apart from farming. At the end of the trip tourists generally purchase local handicrafts as a thank giving gesture. This also helps them to make their life better.

Objective of study

1. To understand the impact of homestays on the economy, socio-cultural aspects and livelihoods of local people of Darjeeling hill region.
2. To study the impact on economy and financial stability among the unemployed of the region
3. To study the impact on socio-cultural aspects of the region
4. To find out the changes of livelihoods and its impact especially on the empowerment of women of the region.

Review of Literature

Debanjan Basak, Arghadeep Bose, Subham Roy, Indrajit Roy Chowdhury, Bipul Chandra Sarkar (2021) - Understanding sustainable homestay tourism as a driving factor of tourist's satisfaction through structural equation modelling: A case of Darjeeling Himalayan region, India.

This research has been done on sustainable homestay tourism as a method to promote economic growth while protecting local culture and heritage and sustainably managing the environment for long-term benefits. Homestay tourism in rural regions has created some jobs, but only to a limited degree. However, in the case of Darjeeling's Himalayan region, homestay tourism has a bright future, and it may be a viable source of revenue in the future only if promoted in a sustainable way. The region needs more educated individuals rather than more environmental experts to have sustainable homestay tourism. That is why the researchers intended to do this study, which is unique because it will reveal tourist satisfaction associated with sustainable homestay tourism. All stakeholders, including residents, should understand the environmental, economic, and socio-cultural implications of homestay tourism and how it affects visitor contentment. All owners and stakeholders should focus on three essential elements of sustainable development, i.e., making it more economically viable, socially equitable, and environmentally responsible.

Sumedha Agarwal, Shashank Mehra (2019) - SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONTRIBUTIONS OF HOMESTAYS: A CASE OF TIRTHAN VALLEY IN HIMACHAL PRADESH (INDIA).

This research has been done on the locals who now believe that tourism activities have become a tool towards rise in the level of income, enhanced their standard of living and created more job opportunities. Tourism activities have made the valley more popular in both the national and international arenas and are helping in publicising the natural and cultural assets of the area. This study offers several implications for the success of the homestay lodging industry. First, this study contributes to the theoretical literature on homestay tourism from the perspectives of the local population. Second, the current study contributes to the research by exploring various criteria on which economic benefits can be explored. Third, the study also has practical implications for the policymakers and the practitioners as they can utilise the study for destination planning and development.

Nem Raj and Mayank Rana, (2022) - Development and growth of homestay in Himachal Pradesh.

This research on increasing number of home stays in all the districts of Himachal Pradesh concludes that Homestays are giving an opportunity to rural people for their socio - economic development and also contributing positively in the rural community. This also shows that there is a positive scope in the development and growth of Homestays and rural tourism in Himachal Pradesh. Sustainable, rural tourism, and pro-poor tourism. Homestay is gaining popularity in all districts of Himachal Pradesh but some districts still need special attention from the Government.

Dr. Nirmala K. D (2021) - Impact of Homestay Tourism On The Local Community: A Study of Homestay Operator's Perspective in Kodagu District of Karnataka.

The study was undertaken to understand the homestay operator's perception of the impact of homestay tourism on the economic, socio-cultural and environmental impact on the local community. The homestay operators had positive perceptions about the economic impact of homestays on the local community especially for the development of local industries, generating employment avenues leading to increased incomes for the people. Employment opportunities have increased leading to enhanced incomes and improvement in quality of life. This is one of the reasons for homestay programs to thrive in the region. But the respondents felt that there is more scope for improvement of public facilities. With respect to socio-cultural impact, the respondents felt that homestay tourism has led to preservation of host community culture and paved the way for its transmission to the younger generation through the process of socialisation and promoting the understanding of local culture to the outsiders.

Methodology For the objective of the research to be achieved, a qualitative research approach has been undertaken. The case study method was chosen to conduct the research. Face to face in-depth interviews, personal field notes were used to collect the data for the study. The case study method helped to gain an in-depth knowledge of the community as it involved interactions with the locals and having a better understanding of their perceptions. The research work included primary and secondary. To obtain the maximum output, the data was collected from three perspectives – firstly, the secondary sources like magazines and research articles were studied. Secondly, individual interviews were conducted with homestay operators and local vendors and service providers; and thirdly, field observation was done to analyse the community participation from an academicians' perspective.

Findings

For research, the Makaibari tea estate in Darjeeling district has been undertaken along with other areas. Makaibari was the first garden to be certified for trade in the world. It was one of the first few to be awarded fair trade certifications. In 1988, it was the first garden to be awarded/ certified as a fully organic tea garden. Makaibari produces around one lakh kg of tea annually. Makaibari has organised 'home stay' arrangements in the villages around the tea estate. Comfortable accommodation and food is provided, plus the tourists (foreigner and Indian) not only get to know the tea garden, but also the life-style of the villagers. The 'home stay' programmes started by the management "where Gorkha tea workers host visitors in chalets attached to their own homes", this provides extra income for the workers.

Unity in business ventures- There are twenty four Home stays in Makaibari but the booking of the same is done centrally. This idea helps the owners to maintain a healthy relationship between themselves. The process of booking comes in turn to them. That way all the twenty four Homestay owners get business.

This idea is basically decided so that none is deprived of business and all of them develop economically and move forward with the business, hand-in -hand.

This study collected responses from 2 formal and 4 informal interviews conducted at 6 different homestays with 4 female owners in the villages of Makaibari, Kursong, and Darjeeling. The interviews were conversational, starting by collecting general information about the homestay itself, including its opening date, amount of rooms, guests hosted, and cost per night. The interview questions then shifted to the opening and maintenance of each homestay. The results from personal interviews in Makaibari, Kursong, and Darjeeling villages are summarised below. When asked about their main primary motivation for opening a homestay, women overwhelmingly answered that their motive was the prospect of a reliable source of income. Some of the women interviewed identified their homestay as currently providing their primary source of income, while some of them said it was their secondary source of income. Prior to opening the homestay, many of the women were unemployed, sustaining off of income from agriculture, and handicraft production (N. Bhujel, formal interview, December 31, 2022, A. Chhetri, informal interview, December 31, 2022). The next section of the interview focused on the economic benefits women had experienced since opening the homestay, and its general impact on their perceived standard of living. Some women interviewed confirmed increased financial stability as the most immediate, tangible benefit from owning a homestay, with one woman remarking, "Things were quite difficult before actually...we had nothing. My mother struggled to provide for us. Things have become much easier for us now that we have this homestay... money is no longer a concern". Moreover, 2 of the women interviewed shared that the income generated from their homestay had significantly improved their standard of living, allowing them to access better food, higher quality clothing, and increasing their level of personal hygiene. Several men also mentioned better health and wellbeing of their children as a benefit of their income. When asked how their income from the homestay was being utilised at the intra household level, the two most common answers provided in the interviews were on children's education, and covering household expenses, including utilities such as water and electricity, and groceries.. All 12 of the women interviewed with children communicated that after providing for basic, everyday needs, the education of their children was their most central concern, and expressed that their homestays had helped to alleviate some of their anxiety about paying for tuition. Women also reported spending income from the homestay on various social projects within their communities.

The concept of homestay started in 2008 with only two homestays in the Makaibari area of Darjeeling district. Foreigners who visit the very famous tourist destination, Makaibari Tea Factory, prefer to stay in homestays as they get a home away from home atmosphere here.

Homestays have improved the economical conditions of Makaibari especially. The daily wage earners who work at the tea factory earns up to 240 - 250 rupees per day which is insufficient to fulfil their basic need , thus by providing homestay they earn up to 1000 - 1500 per day, which helps them to cope up with their basic needs. The concept of homestay plays an important role in the spread of culture and tradition as they provide traditional cooked local food to their guests and also allows them to learn how to cook the local food. Homestays have positively affected the livelihood of the local residents of Makaibari , by providing the facility of homestay to the tourist they have increased their earnings and therefore they are able to send their children to english medium schools and are able to make their children highly educated by sending them to good colleges for degree and diploma courses as well. The surrounding areas of the homestays such as restaurants, cafes, grocery shops etc. have significantly increased their sales and earns much more revenue from the tourists who stay at the nearby homestays. Thus the local places have also been uplifted through the concept of homestays. The womens of the houses which are offering homestays are gradually becoming financially independent . They are earning money through selling hand made dishes to the guests. They have started the business of hand knitted sweaters and shawls. They prepare various kinds of organic pickles like home made bamboo pickle, garlic pickle etc and honey which they sell at quite good prices to their guests. Thus the housewives are earning money and supporting their families. Most European backpackers who visit Darjeeling prefer to stay at homestays of Makaibari as they are aesthetic as well as budget friendly. Number of homestays have predominantly increased in the past few years . Indians as well as foreigners are knowing more about it from the tourists who have already visited and experienced it. They encourage their family and friends to visit the place. Homestays treat their guests as family and also help them to discover surrounding places and give them a vast knowledge of the crops grown there , livelihood of people etc. Guest feedback received the statement that "I WOULD PREFER A HOMESTAY OVER A HOTEL OR LODGE DUE TO IT'S AFFINITY" , says a guest who stayed at a homestay in Makaibari. Further, sharing her experience she added that it didn't feel like a hotel rather it had a home away from home atmosphere . Guests are treated as family , they make food together with the guests and help them to discover surrounding places . To ensure maximum comfort to the guest is the first priority of a homestay. It leaves such a good impression on the guests that they revisit it again.

Conclusion This study examined the growth and development of Home stays in Darjeeling district. Today homestay is the essential source of income in the semi-urban area of Darjeeling district. Number of homestays has been developed every year from 2018 to 2022. It has been noticed that the area in Darjeeling district like Mirik, Kursong, Darjeeling, Makaibari which were already popular for their tourist destination have contributed significantly in the development of Homestays. The concept of homestay tourism is still new and developing throughout Darjeeling. In conclusion, it can be said that home-stay has become a mechanism for employment generation for Women in Darjeeling Hills and moving towards growth. The local people are becoming aware of the positive impacts of the home-stay. To a great extent, it has been able to create employment opportunities for many unemployed people of the hills, especially women. The home-stay business has a great future perspective in the rural areas of Darjeeling hills and can surely be an alternative option for income generation business. Though the Government is taking good initiative for its sustainability when plan, policy, strategy, and program are introduced must be people-friendly. All the owners, stakeholders should work on and progress on three keys of sustainable development: making it more economically viable, socially equitable and culturally rich to preserve its heritage.

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